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Definitivni program i knjiga sažetaka

Programme and Book of Abstracts

22. - 24. april 2010
Beograd, Srbija

www.pedsurgery-beograd.com

Uticaj prehospitalne primene sedativa na preživljavanje i konačan izgled lečenja dece sa kraniocerebralnim povredama

The impact of prehospital sedative administration on the survival rate and the final outcome of childrens treatment with craniocerebral injuries

D. Stanić, B. Drašković, A. Uram-Benka, G. Turanjanin-Tomić, G. Rakić, S. Vuletić

Institut za zdravstvenu zaštitu dece i omladine Vojvodine,

Klinika za dečiju hirurgiju, Novi Sad

Institute of Child and Adolescent Health Care of Vojvodina

Clinic of Paediatric Surgery

Uvod: Povrede glave su vodeći uzrok smrti kod politraumatizovane dece. U prehospitalnim uslovima, u ranoj, inicijalnoj fazi zbrinjavanja povređenog deteta, značajne karike u lancu predstavljaju: optimalna oksigenacija, endotrahealna intubacija i odgovarajući vid ventilacije, prevencija hipotenzije, pozicija glave, primena analgetika i sedativa tokom transporta u trauma centar. **Cilj:** Cilj istraživanja je bio da se utvrdi značaj primene sedativa u prehospitalnim uslovima, na preživljavanje i krajnji ishod lečenja dece sa izolovanim kraniocerebralnim povredama, koja ne zahtevaju operativno lečenje. **Metod:** Istraživanje je bilo kliničko, prospektivno, delom retrospektivno, obuhvatilo je 60 ispitanika sa izolovanim kraniocerebralnim povredama koje ne zahtevaju hiruško lečenje, uzrasta do 17 godina, Glasgow Coma Scora (GCS) manjeg od 8. Pacijenti su bili podeljeni u dve grupe od po 30 ispitanika. Prvu grupu su činili pacijenti koji su prehospitalno zbrinuti na odgovarajući način, a drugu oni koji to nisu. Akcenat je bio stavljen na primenu sedativa u ranoj fazi zbrinjavanja, u obe grupe. **Rezultati:** Grupe su bile uniformne po uzrastu, polu i vrednosti GCS. U grupi I (sa odgovarajućim ranim prehospitalnim tretmanom) 43,3% ispitanika je primilo sedativ, u odnosu na grupu II gde je taj procenat iznosio 3,3 %. U grupi preživelih ispitanika sedacija je primenjena kod 35,1% ispitanika, a u grupi umrlih kod svega 4,3%. Multiplom regresionom analizom, došlo se do podataka da izostanak primene sedativa prehospitalno, ne utiče na preživljavanje pacijenata, ali ima uticaja na krajnji ishod lečenja. **Zaključak:** Izostanak sedacije u prehospitalnoj fazi lečenja, ukazuje na lošiji krajnji ishod lečenja dece sa izolovanim kraniocerebralnim povredama.

Introduction: Head injuries are a leading cause of death in politraumatized children. The following are important in prehospital conditions: optimal oxigenation, endotracheal intubation and appropriate mode of ventilation, prevention of hypotension, head position, analgesia and sedation during the transport to a trauma centre. **Aim:** To determine the impact of prehospital sedation on the survival rate and the final outcome of children's treatment with isolated craniocerebral injuries. **Methods:** The study included clinical, prospective and partly retrospective research. The research included 60 patients with isolated craniocerebral injuries, aged up to 17, Glasgow Coma Score less than 8, which didn't require surgical treatment. The subjects were divided into two groups of 30. The first group included the patients who were provided appropriate prehospital treatment, and the second group included the subjects who were not. The administration of sedative in prehospital treatment was emphasised. **Results:** The groups were uniform in relation to the age, sex and value of GCS of the subjects. In the first group the percentage of sedation was larger (43,3%) in comparison to the second group with an inadequate initial treatment (3,3%). In the group of those who survived 35,1% of patients were sedated, compared to the group of patients who died (4,3%). By multiple regression analysis was shown that the sedation in prehospital period didn't affect the survival rate but had an impact on a better outcome of treatment. **Conclusion:** Lack of administration of sedatives in the prehospital period, indicates a poorer outcome of children's treatment with isolated craniocerebral injuries.